

NONLINEAR ANALYSIS OF TWO-LAYERED BEAMS WITH INTERLAYER SLIP

José Marcio F. Calixto
School of Engineering
Federal University of Minas Gerais
Belo Horizonte, Minas Gerais, Brazil

Dan L. Wheat
Civil Engineering Department
The University of Texas
Austin, Texas, USA

ABSTRACT

The theory is presented for a two-layered one dimensional elastic member acting either as a beam or beam-column and including both connector and geometric nonlinearities. An energy approach is employed in the formulation from which the governing differential equations and associated boundary conditions are explicitly derived through variational procedures. Tests of two-layered wood beams are conducted to verify the theory and good correlation is achieved.

Keywords: Nonlinear analysis, incomplete composite action, differential equations, wood.

INTRODUCTION

Layered beams have been used in structural applications for many years. They are usually composed of two or more different materials attached to each other by a mechanical connector or elastomeric adhesive. Although simply constructed, layered beams are extremely complex to analyze. In some widely used cases such as layered wood construction connected with nails, there exists an interlayer slip of sufficient magnitude to have a major effect on the deflections and stresses of the beams. Also for moderate levels of slip, the nailed joints between the wood members exhibit nonlinear behavior. These facts have led to an extensive investigation, both experimental and analytical [1, 2, 3], of layered beams with interlayer slip. These studies have documented very well not only the effects of the slip and the nonlinear behavior of the nailed joints in layered beams but also the existence of displacements approaching the depth of the members before failure for wood beams. On the other hand, all analytical models developed so far are within the framework of small deflection theory with some including the effects of the nonlinear behavior of the connectors.

In this paper, a theory for the nonlinear analysis of two-layered beams is presented [4]. Both the effects of finite displacements and nonlinear behavior of the connectors are included. By finite displacements it is meant displacements which are no longer small with respect to the depth of beam but still small with respect to the beam length. An energy approach is employed in the formulation from which the governing differential equations and associated boundary conditions are explicitly derived through variational procedures. Two-layered wood beams were built and tested to verify the developed theory.

Previous Research

The behavior of layered beams with interlayer slip has been treated by several authors [1, 5, 6, 7]. Although developed separately, these theories assume infinitesimal displacements, continuous shear connection between layers, and constant connector spacing along the beam length. They also assume a linear connector behavior except for Goodman's in which a nonlinear variation between the force on a connector and its deformation can take place. Goodman in his work has also compared these theories and showed that all of them provided the same governing equations.

GENERAL THEORY

Assumptions

The basic governing equations for a two-layered beam including interlayer slip are derived next. In the analysis of this beam, the following assumptions are introduced:

- 1 - the beam, the applied loads, and the deformations lie in a plane; the plane of the loads is a plane of symmetry for the beam;
- 2 - the beam is assumed to be slender; that is, the length of the beam is much larger than its lateral dimensions;
- 3 - transverse displacements may be finite while longitudinal displacements are infinitesimal;
- 4 - only normal strains parallel to the axis of the beam are considered and in each layer they are constant through the depth for axial deformations and vary linearly through the depth due to bending.
- 5 - at every section of the beam, each layer deflects the same amount and there is no separation between them.
- 6 - materials are assumed to be linearly elastic except for the connectors which may be nonlinear elastic;
- 7 - nonlinear behavior is not so widespread that unloading of the wood or the connectors would occur;
- 8 - the geometric and elastic properties of each layer are constant along the length, but can be different from one layer to the other;
- 9 - the shear connection between layers is continuous along the length; that is, discrete deformable connectors are assumed closely spaced with respect to the length of the beam to be replaced by a continuous shear connection;
- 10 - there is no friction at the interface between the two layers; the interaction between the layers is from the connector load-slip characteristics.

Formulation

The formulation begins by defining the internal strains assumed to resist the external loads on the beam. For a two-layered member, the normal strains induced longitudinally in each layer are given by:

$$\epsilon_{xxi} = \frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] \quad (1)$$

where

u_i = axial displacement at midheight of layer i of the member; and

w = transverse displacement at midheight of the member.

Equation 1 is a component of the Green's strain tensor in the Lagrangian formulation. For the range of the magnitudes of the displacements and strains prescribed in the assumptions, Equation 1 can be reduced to:

$$\epsilon_{xxi} = \frac{du_i}{dx} - z \frac{d^2w}{dx^2} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{dw}{dx} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

where z is measured from the geometric centroid of layer i .

The slip is computed by considering the geometry of the deformation between the original and final positions at the interface of the two layers. This slip can be related to the displacements by the following expression:

$$\Delta = u_{i+1} - u_i - \frac{1}{2} (h_{i+1} + h_i) \frac{dw}{dx} \quad (3)$$

where

Δ = slip between layers i and $i+1$; and

h_i = thickness of layer i .

The load-slip relationship for different types of connectors has been the subject of several studies. Different expressions have been derived based mainly on experimental data. For this study, the empirical relationship presented by Foschi and Bonac [8] for commonly used nails in wood construction is employed. This relationship expresses the force on the nail - in single shear - as a function of the joint slip, the slope of the initial tangent to the slip curve, the slope of the tangent to the slip curve at large slips and the intercept of the asymptote at ultimate load with the force axis. The load-slip curve is:

$$F = (P_0 + P_1 \Delta) \left[1 - \exp \left(- \frac{k \Delta}{P_0} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

where

F = force in the nail;

k = initial tangent modulus;

P_0 = intercept of the asymptote at ultimate load;

P_1 = slope at large slips; and

Δ = slip in the joint.

The complete behavior of the member can be related to the applied loads through the consideration of the total potential energy. Four sources contribute to the total potential energy in the member:

- 1 - The axial strain energy in each layer;
- 2 - the flexural strain energy in each layer;
- 3 - the slip of the connectors between the two layers; and
- 4 - the externally applied lateral and axial loads.

The potential energy functional then becomes:

$$U = \sum_{i=1}^2 \int_{V_i} \frac{E_i}{2} \varepsilon_{xxi}^2 dv_i - \int_{L_e} q w dx - \sum_{i=1}^2 P_i u_i + \int_{L_e} \frac{n\Delta}{s} (P_o + P_1 \Delta) \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{k\Delta}{P_o}\right) \right] dx \quad (5)$$

where

- U = total potential energy;
- E_i = modulus of elasticity of layer i;
- V_i = volume of layer i;
- L_e = length of the member;
- n = number of rows of connectors between the layers
- s = spacing of the connectors;
- q = uniformly distributed lateral load; and
- P_i = axial load applied on the centroid of layer i.

Expressions for ε_{xxi} and Δ are given by Equations 2 and 3 respectively. In Equation 5, the first term is the internal strain energy due to the normal strains in each layer, the second and third are, respectively, the work done by the external lateral and axial loads while the last term corresponds to the strain energy due to the slip of the connectors.

Governing Equations

The principle of virtual work requires that the total potential energy have a stationary value at the equilibrium position. Through the usual procedures associated with the calculus of variations, this requirement is expressed as

$$\delta U = 0 \quad (6)$$

where δ is the variational operator. Using this operator on the energy functional expressed by Equation 5, with the proper substitutions of Equations 2 and 3, leads to the following system of nonlinear, coupled differential equations:

$$E_1 A_1 \left(\frac{d^2 u_1}{dx^2} + w' \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right) + \frac{P_o n}{s} \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{k\Delta}{P_o} \right) \right] \exp\left(-\frac{k\Delta}{P_o}\right) + \frac{n\Delta P_1}{s} \left[2 - \left(2 - \frac{k\Delta}{P_o} \right) \right] \exp\left(-\frac{k\Delta}{P_o}\right) = 0 \quad (7a)$$

$$E_2 A_2 \left(\frac{d^2 u_2}{dx^2} + w' \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right) - \frac{P_o n}{s} \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{k\Delta}{P_o} \right) \right] \exp\left(-\frac{k\Delta}{P_o}\right) - \frac{n\Delta P_1}{s} \left[2 - \left(2 - \frac{k\Delta}{P_o} \right) \right] \exp\left(-\frac{k\Delta}{P_o}\right) = 0 \quad (7b)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^2 E_i I_i \left(\frac{d^4 w}{dx^4} \right) + \frac{kn\Delta'}{2s} (h_1 + h_2) \left(2 - \frac{k\Delta}{P_o} \right) \exp\left(-\frac{k\Delta}{P_o}\right) - E_1 A_1 \left(\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right) \left(u_1' + \frac{1}{2} w'^2 \right) - E_2 A_2 \left(\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right) \left(u_2' + \frac{1}{2} w'^2 \right) + \frac{n\Delta P_1}{2s} (h_1 + h_2) \left[2 - \left(2 - \frac{4k\Delta}{P_o} + \frac{k^2 \Delta^2}{P_o^2} \right) \exp\left(-\frac{k\Delta}{P_o}\right) \right] - q = 0 \quad (7c)$$

The associated essential and natural boundary conditions are:

$$\left[E_1 A_1 \left(u_1'(0) + \frac{w'(0)}{2} \right) - P_1^0 \right] \delta u_1(0) = 0 \quad (8a)$$

$$\left[E_1 A_1 \left(u_1'(L_e) + \frac{w'(L_e)}{2} \right) - P_1 L_e \right] \delta u_1(L_e) = 0 \quad (8b)$$

$$\left[E_2 A_2 \left(u_2'(0) + \frac{w'(0)}{2} \right) - P_2 0 \right] \delta u_2(0) = 0 \quad (8c)$$

$$\left[E_2 A_2 \left(u_2'(L_e) + \frac{w'(L_e)}{2} \right) - P_2 L_e \right] \delta u_2(L_e) = 0 \quad (8d)$$

$$\left\{ \sum_{i=1}^2 E_i I_i \frac{d^3 w}{dx^3} - \frac{n P_0}{2s} (h_1 + h_2) \left[1 - \left(1 - \frac{k\Delta}{P_0} \right) \exp \left(-\frac{k\Delta}{P_0} \right) \right] + \frac{E_1 A_1}{2} (w^3 + 2w u_1') + \frac{E_1 A_1}{2} (w^3 + 2w u_2') \right. \\ \left. - \frac{n\Delta P_1}{2s} (h_1 + h_2) \left[2 - \left(2 - \frac{k\Delta}{P_0} \right) \exp \left(-\frac{k\Delta}{P_0} \right) \right] \right\} \delta w \Big|_0^{L_e} = 0 \quad (8e)$$

$$\left[\sum_{i=1}^2 E_i I_i \frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} \right] \delta w \Big|_0^{L_e} = 0 \quad (8f)$$

The analysis of Equations 8 indicates that any combination of the essential and natural boundary conditions can be specified at the ends of the beam. Physically the essential boundary conditions correspond to cases in which the displacements are prescribed at ends while the natural boundary conditions correspond to cases where the axial force, shear or moment are known at the ends. Equations 8 also present explicitly expressions for the internal axial and shear forces as well as bending moment in each layer. These expressions correspond to the coefficients of the terms in which the variational operator is applied.

Solution of the Governing Equations

Several methods for solving Equations 7 along with selected boundary conditions, were attempted, including Fourier series and finite difference. The nonlinear terms called for abandoning the Fourier series approach while convergence was not achieved in the nonlinear algebraic equations acquired in the finite difference method.

A shooting method [9,10] procedure was used next to solve the system of equations. In a shooting method, the set of values of the unspecified conditions at the initial point of the domain-- the left end-- is assumed, and the differential equations are integrated numerically over the domain to the terminal point-- the right end. If the computed terminal values satisfy the specified terminal conditions, the problem has been solved. If they do not, which is the normal course of events, the differences between the computed and the specified terminal conditions are used to adjust the initial conditions at the left end. Since in this case the system of differential equations is nonlinear, the adjustment of the missing initial solution is an iterative process.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Nailed two-layered wood beams were constructed and tested to verify the analytical theory. Deflections, strains and slips at several locations along the length of the beams were monitored and recorded for comparison with the theory [4]. Each beam was composed of a joist nailed to a single layer of sheathing. Since the primary objective of the theory is to describe the behavior of layered beams in the finite displacement range, the joists were placed flat; thus bending

occurred through their minor axis and finite displacements could be obtained for a medium length beam under moderate loads.

For the beams, the joists were nominal 150 x 50 mm and 200 x 50 mm, southern yellow pine no. 2 grade kiln-dried to 15 percent moisture content. The sheathing for all cases was 18 mm APA southern pine and the connectors were 6d bright common nails spaced every 178 mm.

Prior to the construction of each beam, modulus of elasticity (MOE) for the joists and sheathing were determined experimentally through a simple beam test. Being an important factor on the behavior of layered beams, the load-slip curve of the 6d bright common nails was carefully determined through a series of simple tests from which the parameters employed in Foschi's equation were determined. An average of each one of the parameters was then calculated from which the values for k , P_1 , and P_0 were 4492 N/mm, 173 N/mm and 467 N respectively.

COMPARISON OF THEORETICAL ANALYSIS WITH EXPERIMENTS

A typical midspan deflection curve for a tested beam 1 is given in Figure 1. The geometric and material properties corresponding to this beam are found in Appendix II. In this case, good agreement is still obtained for magnitudes of deflections substantially larger than the depth of the members since the depth of the joists for the beam was 38 mm.

Figure 1 - Load versus Midspan Deflection for Beam 1

The comparison of the slip at the end for tested beam 4 is shown in Figure 2. Even with magnitudes of slip above 3 mm, good correlation is obtained with the analysis results. Figure 4 depicts the comparative results of the midspan strain for beam 1 at the bottom fiber of the joist. Good comparison is achieved as long as the strains remain in the elastic region. For strains above the elastic limit (4000 micro), the analysis predicts a stiffer behavior.

Figure 2 - Midspan Load versus End Slip for Beam 4

Figure 3 - Midspan Load versus Maximum Tensile on the Joist at Midspan for Beam 1

CONCLUSION

A consistent theory for the analysis of two-layered beams with interlayer slip and including the effects of finite displacements and nonlinear behavior for the connectors has been presented. By finite displacements it is meant displacements in the order of magnitude of the depth of the members. An energy formulation is applied from which explicit expressions for the axial and shear forces and bending moments in each layer at every point of the beam are derived. Any combination of the essential and natural boundary conditions can also be specified at the ends of the beam. Verification of the theory is performed with laboratory tested of two-layered wood beams and good correlation is reached.

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APPENDIX I - GEOMETRIC AND MATERIAL PROPERTIES OF TESTED BEAMS

Beam 1 -

Span: 2133 mm

Joist: $E = 15,87 \times 10^6 \text{ kN/m}^2$

Size: 139 x 37 mm

Plywood sheathing

$E_{\text{axial}} = 5,06 \times 10^6 \text{ kN/m}^2$

$E_{\text{bend}} = 9,11 \times 10^6 \text{ kN/m}^2$

Size: 203 x 18 mm

Connector spacing: 178 mm

Number of rows of connectors: 3

Beam 4 -

Span: 2133 mm

Joist: $E = 14,29 \times 10^6 \text{ kN/m}^2$

Size: 186 x 40 mm

Plywood sheathing

$E_{\text{axial}} = 5,89 \times 10^6 \text{ kN/m}^2$

$E_{\text{bend}} = 10,71 \times 10^6 \text{ kN/m}^2$

Size: 254 x 17 mm

Connector spacing: 178 mm

Number of rows of connectors: 3